

Effect of plant growth regulators on yield components and rice quality. Dera Ismail Khan, NWFP, Pakistan, 1986 summer.

Treatment ^a	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./plant)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain weight (g)	Sterility (%)	Abortive kernels (%)	Grain yield (g/pot)	Protein content (%)
Control	81 c	12 b	103 c	21 b	10 c	3 b	23 c	7 b
Gibberellic acid (GA ₃) 100 ppm at panicle emergence	92 a	16 a	114 b	22 a	8 b	2 a	38 b	8 a
Indoleacetic acid (IAA) 100 ppm at panicle emergence	89 b	16 a	117 a	22 a	7 a	3 b	40 a	8 a

^a In a column, numbers followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at 5% level of probability by DMRT.

Crop management

Nursery management for rice grown in intermediate deep water

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Experiments on seedbed management were conducted in a farmer's field during 1985 and 1986 wet seasons. Soil was an alluvial, sandy loam type with pH 6.0, CEC 12 meq/ 100 g soil, 0.74% organic C, and 4 ppm available P.

Seedlings of Tilakkachari (an improved selection) and CR1018 (high-yielding variety) were grown by sowing seeds at low (200 kg seeds/ha) and high density (400 kg seeds/ha) with three levels of fertilizer (Table 1).

Seedlings were transplanted at 40 and 60 d after seeding. The submergence water level in the main field varied from 15 to 60 cm during most of crop growth.

Rice plants grown from seedlings raised in the low seed density nursery performed better (productive tillers, grains/panicle, and yield) than plants grown from seedlings raised in the high density nursery (Table 1). Plants grown from seedlings that received N₃₀P₁₅ in the nursery bed also produced significantly higher yield than treatment N₃₀P₀ or no NP.

Applying N₃₀P₁₅ in the nursery followed by topdressed N₃₀ as urea supergranule further ameliorated

Table 1. Effects of seed rate and fertilizer in nursery on growth and yield of transplanted rice varieties under intermediate submergence (15-60 cm). Kharagpur, India, 1985 and 1986 wet seasons.

Treatment	1985			1986		
	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Variety						
Tilakkachari	213	101	3.7	271	99	4.7
CR1018	323	119	5.2	270	134	4.8
LSD (0.05)	72	2	0.4	ns	6	ns
Seed rate (kg/ha)						
200	284	116	4.5	272	123	4.8
400	252	104	4.3	269	110	4.7
LSD (0.05)	14	3	0.1	ns	2	ns
Fertilizer (kg/ha)						
N ₀ P ₀	235	104	4.0	258	108	4.0
N ₃₀ P ₀	277	108	4.5	268	117	4.9
N ₃₀ P ₁₅	292	118	4.7	288	124	5.3
LSD (0.05)	17	4	0.2	9	2	0.3

Table 2. Effects of seedling age and fertilizer in nursery on growth and yield of transplanted rice varieties under intermediate submergence (15-60 cm). Kharagpur, India, 1985 and 1986 wet seasons.

Treatment	1985			1986		
	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Variety						
Tilakkachari	252	117	3.9	238	106	4.9
CR1018	294	149	5.7	267	133	5.4
LSD (0.05)	ns	15	0.1	ns	11	0.4
Seedling age (d)						
40	256	132	4.4	244	114	5.1
60	290	134	5.2	261	124	5.2
LSD (0.05)	24	ns	0.2	15	6	ns
Fertilizers (kg/ha) in nursery						
N ₀ P ₀	246	120	4.2	223	109	4.6
N ₃₀ P ₀	272	128	4.8	239	118	5.1
N ₃₀ P ₁₅	279	138	5.0	251	124	5.2
Fertilizers (kg/ha) in nursery and in field						
N ₃₀ P ₁₅ and N ₃₀ P ₀ (top-dressing)	295	146	5.3	298	127	5.8
LSD (0.05)	10	4	0.2	8	3	0.2

submergence stress (increased growth and significantly higher grain yield) (Table 2). Older seedlings tolerated

intermediate submergence better than did younger seedlings. Semidwarf variety CR1018 performed

better than improved tall variety Tilakkachari, which grows locally under submergence. □

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Effect of continuous application of ammonium sulfate and urea on irrigated rice

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We studied the effect of continuous application of ammonium sulfate on rice yield and on some physicochemical properties of wetland soil.

The clayey soil had pH 6.2 (slightly acidic); 0.12% total N (low); 150 ppm available P (fairly high); 19.8, 7.9, 0.8 meq Ca, Mg, K/100 g soil (high); and 8

ppm $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ content (low). N was deficient and S was below the critical 9 ppm level.

The experiment was established in 1984 wet season (WS) after a simple trial to identify the problem of plant yellowing despite the application of urea. The rice crop was observed to respond to the application of ammonium sulfate.

Twelve treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications (see table). P as TSP and K as KCl were applied (60 kg each) in treatments 2 to 12.

Grain yield was higher when S was applied, at any level. The significant increase in yield was due to N.

Effect of S on grain yield (14% moisture) of IR54. Ujung Pandang, Indonesia, 1984 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
Control	2.7
20 kg S/ha as ammonium sulfate	3.9
0 S, 20 kg N/ha as urea	3.7
40 kg S/ha	4.4
0 S, 40 kg N/ha	4.3
60 kg S/ha	4.8
0 S, 60 kg N/ha	4.4
80 kg S/ha	4.4
0 S, 80 kg N/ha	4.2
100 kg S/ha	4.6
0 S, 100 kg N/ha	4.3
0 S, 0 N, 26.4 kg P, 49.8 kg K/ha	3.0
LSD (0.05)	0.6
(0.01)	0.8
CV (%)	11.8

Application of P and K without S or N did not have any significant effect on yield. □

Reaction of IR20 rice to carbofuran and urea

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The reaction of IR20 rice to combinations of carbofuran and urea was studied at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU) in summer (Feb-Jun) 1983. The objective was to examine the phytotonic effects of carbofuran and its interaction with N.

The experiment was laid out in a factorial combination of three levels of N (0, 60, and 90 kg N/ha as urea) and four levels of carbofuran (0, 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0 kg ai/ha) in a randomized block design with four replications.

Soil at TNAU (11° N, 77° E, and 427 m above mean sea level) was a Vertisol (clay loam) containing 1.0% organic C, 99-8.0-254 ppm available NPK, 0.7 ppm DTPA-extractable Zn, with pH 8.2 and

Influence of carbofuran (0, 1, 2, 3 kg ai/ha) and N on grain yield of IR20. TNAU, Coimbatore, India, 1983.

N (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	No carbofuran	1 kg	2 kg	3 kg	Mean
0	1.9	2.7	2.9	2.9	2.7
60	3.3	3.8	3.1	2.7	3.3
90	4.2	5.0	3.8	4.1	4.2
Mean	3.2	3.8	3.3	3.2	

	LSD (0.05)
Nitrogen (N)	0.5
Carbofuran (C)	0.9
N×C	1.4

EC 0.3 dS/m. The crop was uniformly fertilized and kept insect free by spraying all plots with phosphamidon on a need basis, including plots treated with insecticide.

Carbofuran was incorporated at planting to ensure minimum loss. N as urea was applied in three splits: 50% basal, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation.

Tiller production, leaf area index,

root production, and grain yield increased with urea application up to 90 kg N/ha and with carbofuran application up to 1.0 kg ai/ha (see table).

Based on costs, the combination 90 kg N/ha and 1.0 kg ai carbofuran/ha was optimum. Costs were \$2.5/kg carbofuran 3% granule, \$0.5/kg N, \$0.2/kg rough rice, and \$2.91 person (for labor). □